

A

Thesis on

**Optimizing Inverse Kinematics for Precision Control of
Industrial Robots with a Novel Adaptive LM and FNN**

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requirements for the award of the degree*

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in

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CANDIDATE’S DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work which is being presented in the research project, entitled “**Optimizing Inverse Kinematics for Precision Control of Industrial Robots with a Novel Adaptive LM and FNN**”, in Partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of **Master of Engineering in Robotics and Automation Engineering** and submitted to **CHANDIGARH UNIVERSITY, Gharuan, Mohali** is an original piece of work carried out by me during the period from January 2024 to July 2024 under the supervision of Dr. Anuj Gupta, Assistant Professor, and Dr. Harjot Singh Gill, Professor, Mechatronics Engineering Department, Chandigarh University, Gharuan, Mohali, Punjab, India.

The matter embodied in this thesis has not been submitted by me for the award of any other degree of any other University/Institute.

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ABSTRACT

Two critical inverse kinematics (IK) problems in industrial robotics are addressed in this thesis: task-free IK and task-specific IK. In addressing task-free IK, a novel adaptive Levenberg-Marquardt (ALM) algorithm is designed to improve four metrics: convergence speed, robustness, and pose accuracy and precision. To solve task-specific IK, a Feedforward Neural Network (FNN) model is introduced. The model leverages recent advancements to achieve four objectives: high accuracy and precision, short training time, and real-time computation. The efficiency of the ALM algorithm and the FNN model is evaluated using the ABB IRB 6700 industrial robot.

A first experiment is carried out to thoroughly test the ALM algorithm against a standard, non-adaptive Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) algorithm and an existing ALM algorithm on a variety of performance metrics, including convergence rate, accuracy, precision, and computational efficiency. Results from this experiment show that the proposed ALM method consistently delivers fewer median pose errors, improved accuracy and precision, and superior computational efficiency, even in near-singular configurations.

A second experiment is conducted to assess the efficiency of the FNN model. The assessment is based on the model's accuracy, precision, and training time. Test results show that, with a substantially shorter training time, the FNN achieves significantly lower values for mean error, standard deviation, and root mean squared error in both joint and Cartesian space predictions. A comparative analysis with existing models demonstrates that the proposed FNN represents a significant improvement over these existing models. Furthermore, the FNN performed the IK task approximately 3.63 times faster than the ALM, solidifying its suitability for real-time control in task-specific IK problems. Finally, the model's predictions exhibit significantly lower standard deviations than the ABB IRB 6700's path repeatability, indicating its potential to enhance real-world trajectory execution.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
Adam	Adaptive Moment Estimation
ANFIS	Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DH	Denavit-Hartenberg
DL	Deep Learning
DOF	Degrees of Freedom
DQN	Deep Q-Network
EA	Evolutionary Algorithm
FNN	Feed-Forward Neural Network
FK	Forward Kinematics
FOA	Fruit Fly Optimization Algorithm
GA	Genetic Algorithm
HTM	Homogenous Transformation Matrix
IK	Inverse Kinematics
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
MP	Moore Penrose
MSE	Mean Squared Error
MX	Mixed
POE	Product of Exponentials
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
RL	Reinforcement Learning
SCARA	Selective Compliance Assembly Robot Arm
SLERP	Spherical Linear Interpolation
TCP	Tool Center Point
UC	Unit Consistent

CHAPTER 1

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

In the current landscape of the fourth industrial revolution, industrial robots have become indispensable assets in various sectors such as automotive manufacturing, electronics assembly, and pharmaceutical production, owing to their programmability, dexterity, and repeatability [1], [2], [3], [4]. They have revolutionized modern manufacturing, offering unparalleled versatility and adaptability to changing production demands, from assembly and welding to pick-and-place tasks and material handling [5]. By performing complex operations with precision and reliability, industrial robots reduce the load on human workers and the risks associated with manual labor. [6].

Precise trajectory planning is essential for industrial robots to perform operations efficiently and accurately [7], [8]. The planning process entails finding the best route for the tool (end effector) to reach targeted locations within its workspace. Joint space and Cartesian space trajectory planning are the two main methods for creating a trajectory [9], [10]. Joint space trajectory planning indirectly defines the path by specifying desired joint angles at specific times [11]. While computationally straightforward, this method lacks direct control over the end effector's path, limiting its suitability for applications requiring precise positioning [12]. In contrast to joint space trajectory planning, Cartesian space trajectory planning directly specifies the required tool's pose, typically using Cartesian coordinates to specify the position of the tool and any of the three orientation representations – Euler angles, quaternions, or rotation matrices – to specify the orientation of the tool [13]. Cartesian space trajectory, therefore, provides intuitive control of the tool. However, this approach demands solving the computationally intensive inverse kinematics (IK) problem to determine corresponding joint configurations [14], [15], [16], [17], [18]. The IK problem is divided into two categories: task-free IK and task-specific IK. Task-specific IK focuses on predicting joint configurations for a given trajectory or a set of connected trajectories within the robot's workspace, whereas task-free IK aims to find all potential joint configurations for any pose within the robot's workspace.

Therefore, this thesis proposes two novel IK solutions to address the limitations of existing task-free and task-specific IK solutions. The first approach focuses on developing a robust and efficient algorithm for task-free IK, which will enable a thorough exploration of all attainable robot poses. The second approach introduces a high-performance Feedforward Neural Network (FNN) model specifically tailored for task-specific IK, with the aim of achieving real-time prediction of joint configurations for precise trajectory execution.

The thesis report is organized into five (5) chapters. The first chapter serves as an introduction. It provides an overview of the report's contents and explains three (3) key concepts used throughout this thesis: industrial robots, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), and finally robot kinematics.

Chapter two (Literature Review) explores the methodologies employed in existing literature for tackling both forward and inverse kinematics of industrial robots. It provides a comprehensive review of existing research, identifying the gaps and limitations present in the methods presented in these research works, and finally formulating the objectives of the thesis based on the identified gaps and limitations.

Chapter three (Methodology) is divided into three subsections. The ABB IRB 6700 model, which serves as a case study for the whole thesis, has its forward kinematics thoroughly examined in the first section of Chapter 3. The second part outlines the creation and application of the ALM algorithm for task-free inverse kinematics, while the final part details the methodology used to develop the FNN model for task-specific inverse kinematics.

Chapter four (Results and Discussion) is divided into two subsections. The initial section assesses the effectiveness of the ALM method in handling task-free inverse kinematics, and the second section evaluates the performance of the FNN model for task-specific inverse kinematics.

The last chapter serves as a concluding chapter, summarizing the findings from the previous chapters and discussing their implications. It contains a concise description of the thesis, emphasizing its major contributions and limitations, and suggesting potential areas for future research and enhancement.

1.2 Industrial Robots

1.2.1 Components of industrial robots

Overall, the composition of industrial robots is a carefully orchestrated integration of mechanical, electrical, and computational elements. **Figure 1.1** depicts this structure.

Figure 1.1 Components of industrial robots

Generally, the mechanical architecture of a robotic arm is made up of a series or parallel arrangement of rigid segments, called links. The endpoint of this chain (the end effector), acts like a robotic hand, enabling the arm to perform various tasks. [19]. The specific point on the end effector where it is located in space during operation is known as the Tool Center Point (TCP). The robot is held firmly to a reference position by a ground link or ground frame, providing stability for the mechanism. The joints come in two main types: revolute joints allow for turning motions, while prismatic joints enable links to slide back and forth. The framework (kinematic chain) for the robotic arm is formed by a sequential interconnection of the various links and joints. The robot's degrees of freedom (DOF), or

the range of independent motions it can execute, are determined by the number of joints in its kinematic chain.

The mechanical structure of the robot interfaces directly with two main electrical components: actuators and sensors. The actuators are responsible for generating the necessary forces and motions to control robot joints to manipulate objects and execute tasks. They include stepper motors, servo motors, and solenoids. The sensors on the other hand are responsible for gathering feedback on the robot's surroundings and monitoring the robot's motions, to enable precise control and adaptation to dynamic conditions. They include proximity sensors, encoders, and tactile sensors.

Control systems are central to the operations of an industrial robot. It guides the movements of the robot using sensor readings, the control system's programming, and operator's commands. Control systems are equipped with sophisticated algorithms that leverage the signal difference between the operator's commands and sensor readings to generate signals for controlling the actuators of the robot. These algorithms are designed for trajectory and motion control, as well as collision avoidance.

1.2.2 Classification of industrial robots

Industrial robots are classified according to their mechanical architecture. Serial and parallel robots are the main classification of industrial robots.

A parallel robot is made up of two connected platforms – one stationary and the other mobile with at least two parallel, independent links, called legs, joining the fixed platform to mobile platform. The moving part of the robot holds the tool. **Figure 1.2** shows an example of a parallel robot (hexapod). The concept of the parallel robots was initially proposed in connection to flight simulators and tire-testing equipment. They have since been used for a variety of operations that require the manipulation of large payloads at high speeds, such as automobile driving simulators. Parallel robots offer several benefits over standard serial robots and are notably useful in assembly and medical applications.

For industrial applications, serial robots are the most popular architecture used. In this architecture, the links are connected in series to form a kinematic chain. Each link is coupled with the preceding link using either a revolving joint, which permits rotation, or a

prismatic joint, which allows sliding. Serial robots have a tool installed on the final link of their kinematic chain, acting as the extension that directly interacts with the environment. Serial robots are best suited to industrial applications because of their wide working area and simple design [20], [21], [22].

Figure 1.2 Parallel robot

Under serial robots, industrial robots are further categorized according to their configuration and workspace. A robot's workspace refers to the area it can physically reach with its end effector, including all possible positions and rotations within that zone. This spatial region is determined by the type (revolute or prismatic) and number of joints the manipulator has and how the joints and links are configured in the kinematic chain. The following are the different classes of robots used in industries today:

Cartesian robot (PPP): A Cartesian robot, often called a gantry robot, is a kind of industrial robot known for moving in straight lines along three intersecting axes: X, Y, and Z. Their

architecture is made up of only prismatic joints. Cartesian robots typically feature a rigid frame, with one or more linear actuators or motors driving motion of the joints along each axis. These robots excel in tasks demanding precise object positioning and handling within a confined workspace, particularly, pick-and-place operations, material handling, and CNC machining. Owing to their simple and straightforward kinematics, Cartesian robots are relatively easy to program and integrate into automated systems. An instance of gantry robot is displayed in **Figure 1.3**.

Figure 1.3 Cartesian robot

Cylindrical robot (RPP): Cylindrical robots are a class of industrial robots known for their cylindrical workspace and joint configuration, which is typically denoted as RPP (Revolute-Prismatic-Prismatic). These robots have a revolute joint at the base, enabling rotation around a vertical axis, followed by two prismatic joints that provide linear movement along both the radial and vertical directions. The work envelope created by

cylindrical robots is the space between two cylinders of the same diameter. Cylindrical robots are suitable for industrial operations such as welding, painting, and material handling, where the operations are focused around cylindrical workpieces or surfaces. An instance of cylindrical robot is displayed **Figure 1.4**.

Figure 1.4 Cylindrical robot

Spherical robot (RRP): Spherical robots possess an RRP (Revolute-Revolute-Prismatic) and special capabilities for a range of applications. These robots have a sequence of two revolute joints and a final prismatic joint. The first joint rotates about the vertical axis, the second rotates about the lateral axis, and the final joint moves linearly along the longitudinal axis. Because of its ability to manoeuvre within a spherical workspace, spherical robots are an excellent choice for operations requiring multi-directional mobility or manipulation in confined spaces. Their ability to manoeuvre over difficult terrain and adapt to changing conditions is crucial in a variety of industries, such as search and rescue, surveillance, and even planetary exploration.

Selective Compliance Assembly Robot Arm (SCARA) robot (RRP): SCARA is a common configuration in industrial robotics and automation. Like spherical robots, SCARA robots have an RRP (Revolute-Revolute-Prismatic) joint configuration. SCARA robots, however, only have joints that rotate around or translate along the vertical axis. SCARA robots have a good blend of flexibility and rigidity, allowing for accurate placement and manipulation in two-dimensional workspaces. SCARA robots are also often compact in size, inexpensive, and operate quickly, making them versatile for a variety of automation tasks. **Figure 1.5** is an image of a SCARA industrial robot.

Figure 1.5 SCARA robot

Articulated robot (RRR): Articulated robots are the most widely used class of industrial robots, and they are capable of complex motion and manipulation tasks. Articulated robots feature a serial chain of revolute joints only, thus forming the RRR (Revolute-Revolute-Revolute) configuration. This arrangement of joints enables rotational movement along several axes, which in turn enables extensive flexibility of the articulated robot to reach various poses within its working envelope. This includes navigating around obstacles,

reaching confined spaces, and manipulating objects from different positions and orientations. Articulated robots are used in tasks that require precision and flexibility such as automotive assembly lines and electronics manufacturing. An example of an articulated robot is displayed in **Figure 1.6**.

Figure 1.6 Articulated robot

1.3 Introduction to AI and ANNs

1.3.1 Artificial intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is among the earliest disciplines in computer science, with a broad scope aimed at emulating human-like cognitive capabilities. Its objectives span various domains, including planning and decision-making, interpreting environmental data through perception and recognition, comprehending human language, and adapting and learning from experiences. These endeavors collectively seek to address everyday challenges by infusing machines such as the industrial robots discussed in this thesis with

abilities similar to human intelligence. AI can be categorized into two classifications: rule-based systems (traditional programming) and machine learning (ML).

1.3.2 Paradigms of artificial intelligence

AI has distinct paradigms for modelling intelligent behaviour in machines. Among these paradigms are rule-based systems, machine learning, and evolutionary algorithms, with each paradigm offering unique perspectives and techniques for solving problems. **Figure 1.7** is a summary of the paradigms of AI.

Figure 1.7 Paradigms of AI

A rule-based system is a type of AI system that operates by applying a sequence of predefined rules to input data to make decisions or perform actions. The rules are written as "if-then" statements, where specific actions or conclusions are triggered based on the satisfaction of certain conditions. This is why rule-based systems are sometimes called traditional programming. Rule-based systems find diverse applications across various fields. In industrial automation, ladder logic within programmable logic controllers (PLCs) utilizes pre-defined rules to control machinery and processes. Fuzzy inference systems (FIS) handle situations with varying degrees of truth, making them suitable for complex decision-making in control systems and image processing, unlike traditional true or false logic systems. Decision support systems (DSS) assist human decision-makers by analyzing data and offering recommendations based on specific rules, while expert systems mimic

the expertise of human specialists in a specific domain through rule-based reasoning for problem-solving and advice.

Unlike rule-based systems machine learning (ML) is paradigm of AI that goes beyond simple decision-making by enabling systems or machines to recognize or ‘learn’ patterns and relationships within data, facilitating decisions or forecasts contingent on the ‘learned’ knowledge rather than solely relying on predefined rules. As defined by Arthur Samuel in his work on developing a self-learning program to play checkers [23], “Machine learning is the field of study that gives computers the ability to learn without being explicitly programmed”.

Evolutionary algorithms (EAs) are optimization techniques based on the process of natural selection and biological evolution. EAs work by maintaining a population of candidate solutions, where each solution is encoded as a chromosome (individual). Within the EA, every member of the population embodies a potential answer to the problem. EAs maintain a population of candidate solutions, select the best (fittest), and create offsprings through crossover and mutation. Offsprings replace weaker solutions, evolving the population towards better ones. EAs explore the solution space iteratively, refining solutions until optimal or satisfactory ones are found. They are versatile tools applicable to diverse optimization problems, from engineering to finance and machine learning. Examples of EAs include genetic algorithms (GA) and Fruit Fly Optimization Algorithm (FOA).

1.3.3 Deep learning

Deep learning (DL) is a specialized subfield of ML which leverages multilayered artificial neural networks (ANNs) to ‘learn’ and extract features from data in a hierarchical manner, similar to how the brain processes information through layers of neurons [24], [25]. ANNs are built with three key layers: the input layer, intermediate (hidden) layers, and output layer. The input layer accepts raw input data, which could be images, text, or numerical features. The intermediate layers, which can range from a few to hundreds or even thousands of layers, extract increasingly abstract features from the input data through a series of nonlinear transformations. Within these hidden layers, interconnected neurons, also called units or nodes, perform calculations. Each neuron combines its weighted inputs, applies a special function (activation function) to this value, and then transmits the resulting

output to neurons in the next layer. The final layer leverages the the processed information from the intermediate layers to generate predictions or classifications. ANNs are trained using optimization algorithms like gradient descent. The network continuously refines the connections between neurons by adjusting weights. This iterative process minimizes the difference between the model's predictions and the actual results. The layered architecture of ANNs empowers them to excel in diverse machine learning tasks. This hierarchical structure allows them to effectively learn intricate patterns and representations from data. Prominent examples of ANNs are multilayer perceptron (MLP) also known as feed-forward neural network (FNN), recurrent neural network (RNN), convolutional neural network (CNN), and deep Q-network (DQN).

1.3.4 Machine learning methods

ML, being it, traditional ML algorithms or DL algorithms employ three methods or approaches to 'learn', namely, supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning [26], [27], [28]. The first approach, supervised learning, entails training models using labelled data to map inputs to outputs [29]. The model learns to map these inputs to outputs, making predictions or classifications based on the provided examples in the labelled data . Decision trees, support vector machines, linear regression, and neural networks are a few examples of powerful algorithms used in supervised learning [30]. Supervised learning thrives in a range of tasks including image recognition, natural language processing, and even medical diagnosis [31].

In contrast, unsupervised learning operates on unlabelled data, seeking to discover patterns and structures embedded in the data with no explicit guidance [32]. K-means clustering, hierarchical clustering, principal component analysis (PCA), and autoencoders are typical algorithms used employed in unsupervised learning. Unsupervised learning excel in tasks like segmenting customers, identifying anomalies, and extracting meaningful features from raw data [33].

Reinforcement learning empowers agents (learners) to learn through trial and error while the agent interacts with and adapts to an environment. With any policy the learner uses, it receives feedback in the form of rewards or penalties, allowing it to refine its actions and improve its policy over time. The agent's purpose is to develop an optimal strategy that

maximizes cumulative rewards and delivers the optimal results in the long term. [34], [35]. RL performs particularly well in tasks thanks demand sequential decision-making. This makes it an effective tool for applications such as gaming, robot control, and self-driving cars. Some prominent algorithms used in RL include Q-learning, policy gradient methods, and actor-critic methods [36].

1.4 Robot Kinematics

Kinematics, a fundamental branch of robotics, serves as the cornerstone for understanding the motion and spatial configuration of robotic mechanisms independent of the forces triggering the motion. Robot kinematics broadly falls into two main branches: position kinematics and differential kinematics.

Position kinematics deals with the static spatial connection between joint positions and the resulting end effector posture (its location and orientation), or vice versa. Differential kinematics, on the other hand, addresses the dynamic connection between joint velocities and the end effector's motion, emphasizing motion over static positions.

Robot kinematics provides the essential framework for analyzing and predicting the movement of robotic systems, thereby influencing their overall performance. This framework analyzes how joint movements (in joint space) translate to the end effector's motion (in Cartesian space). This analysis is called forward kinematics (FK). Conversely, it can also be used to determine the required joint motions (again, in joint space) to achieve a desired end-effector movement (in Cartesian space). This process is known as inverse kinematics (IK).

Inverse kinematics can be further categorized into two types: task-free IK and task-specific IK. While task-free IK aims to find all possible joint configurations for any pose within the robot's workspace, task-specific IK, concentrates on predicting joint configurations for a particular trajectory or set of connected trajectories within the robot's workspace.

1.4.1 Position kinematics

Position offers a mathematical structure to control the robot's pose at any moment in time. The framework can be a FK model (\mathbf{X}) which allows the prediction of the pose of the end-

effector in the workspace required to achieve a desired set of joint angles. **Equation 1.1** represents a FK model. In this equation, the FK function ($f()$) takes the desired joint angles (n representing the number of joints) and maps them to the end effector's pose. In most cases, a FK model is represented as a homogenous transformation matrix (HTM) as shown in **Equation 1.2**.

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{T}_{End\ effector}^{Base} = f(\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n)_{desired} \quad 1.1$$

$$\mathbf{T}_{End\ effector}^{Base} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{xx} & r_{yx} & r_{zx} & t_x \\ r_{xy} & r_{yy} & r_{zy} & t_y \\ r_{xz} & r_{yz} & r_{zz} & t_z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_x & \mathbf{R}_y & \mathbf{R}_z & \mathbf{t}_p \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{t}_p \\ \mathbf{0}^T & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad 1.2$$

In this equation, \mathbf{R} is a 3x3 rotation matrix representing the rotation of the tool referenced from the ground link (base). \mathbf{R}_x , \mathbf{R}_y , and \mathbf{R}_z are unit vectors that describe the tool's orientation referenced from the Cartesian axes and \mathbf{t}_p is a 3x1 translation vector representing the position or translation.

A positional kinematics model may operate as an IK model, enabling the determination of the joint configuration necessary to attain a wanted pose of the tool in the workspace. **Equation 1.3** represents an IK model. Where $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ typically represents the vector of joint angles, and g is the IK function that maps the desired tool pose (\mathbf{X}) to $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. This vector includes the variables that specify the configuration of the robot's joints.

$$\boldsymbol{\theta} = g\mathbf{X}_{desired} = [\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n] \quad 1.3$$

Essentially, position kinematics captures the static characteristics of the robot. When the primary concern is reaching a specific point in space with high precision, such as precise assembly, packaging, and pick and place tasks, position kinematics is used.

Euler angles are three angles – roll (φ), pitch (θ_e), and yaw (ψ) – used to represent the orientation of the tool or gripper beside a rotation matrix, when modelling the position kinematics of robots. The YXZ convention is one of the many ways to represent these angles. In this convention, three rotations occur about the fixed axes of the base in a

particular sequence: initially around the lateral axis (Y), followed by the longitudinal axis (X), and lastly the vertical axis (Z). Thus, the convention chosen determines the order of rotation. **Equations 1.4 to 1.6** expresses the rotation matrix for each rotation.

$$\mathbf{R}_y(\varphi) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\varphi) & 0 & \sin(\varphi) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin(\varphi) & 0 & \cos(\varphi) \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{1.4}$$

$$\mathbf{R}_x(\theta_e) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\theta_e) & -\sin(\theta_e) \\ 0 & \sin(\theta_e) & \cos(\theta_e) \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{1.5}$$

$$\mathbf{R}_z(\psi) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\psi) & -\sin(\psi) & 0 \\ \sin(\psi) & \cos(\psi) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{1.6}$$

Euler angle representation is best visualized using the gimbal system. As illustrated in **Figure 1.8**, the gimbal system is made of three rotating rings, each perpendicular to the others, allowing rotation about three orthogonal axes. Each ring represents one of the axes of rotation (Y, X, and Z) in our Euler angle convention. The inner ring (green ring) allows revolution around the lateral axis. This revolution is a rolling motion in the Euler angle convention. The middle ring (red ring) allows revolution around the longitudinal axis. This motion pitching in the Euler angle convention. The outer ring (blue ring) allows movement around the Z-axis, which corresponds to yaw in the Euler angle convention.

Initially (**Figure 1.8(a)**), the end effector aligns with the fixed coordinate system, with all Euler angles set to zero. This is expressed mathematically in **Equation 1.7**.

$$\mathbf{R}_E = \mathbf{R}_z(0) \cdot \mathbf{R}_y(0) \cdot \mathbf{R}_x(0) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{1.7}$$

(a) $R_z(0) \cdot R_y(0) \cdot R_x(0)$

(b) $R_z(0) \cdot R_x(0) \cdot R_y(\varphi)$

(c) $R_z(0) \cdot R_x(\theta_e) \cdot R_y(\varphi)$

$$(d) R_z(\psi) \cdot R_x(\theta_e) \cdot R_y(\varphi)$$

Figure 1.8 Euler angles (YXZ convention)

As depicted in **Figure 1.8(b)**, the initial rotation occurs about the Y-axis (the inner ring), resulting in the end effector rotating by an angle φ around this axis. This is expressed mathematically in **Equation 1.8**.

$$R_E = R_z(0) \cdot R_x(0) \cdot R_y(\varphi) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\varphi) & 0 & \sin(\varphi) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin(\varphi) & 0 & \cos(\varphi) \end{bmatrix} \quad 1.8$$

As depicted in **Figure 1.8(c)**, the next rotation occurs about the X-axis (the middle ring), resulting in the end effector further rotating by an angle θ around this axis. This is expressed mathematically in **Equation 1.9**.

$$R_E = R_z(0) \cdot R_x(\theta_e) \cdot R_y(\varphi) \\ = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\varphi) & 0 & \sin(\varphi) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin(\varphi) & 0 & \cos(\varphi) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\theta) \\ 0 & \sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad 1.9$$

As depicted in **Figure 1.8(d)**, the next rotation occurs about the Z-axis (the outer ring), resulting in the end effector further rotating by an angle ψ around this axis. This is expressed mathematically in **Equation 1.10**.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{R}_E &= \mathbf{R}_z(\psi) \cdot \mathbf{R}_x(\theta_e) \cdot \mathbf{R}_y(\varphi) \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\psi) & -\sin(\psi) & 0 \\ \sin(\psi) & \cos(\psi) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\varphi) & 0 & \sin(\varphi) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin(\varphi) & 0 & \cos(\varphi) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\theta) \\ 0 & \sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{1.10}
\end{aligned}$$

The HTM presented in **Equation 1.2** can be recalculated using the rotation matrix derived from the Euler angle convention. The resulting matrix is depicted in **Equation 1.11**.

$$\mathbf{T}_{End\ effector}^{Base} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_E & \mathbf{t}_p \\ \mathbf{0}^T & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{1.11}$$

In all, there are twenty four (24) unique conventions for representing Euler angles. These conventions comprise all possible combinations of rotations about the three axes (X, Y, and Z) in different orders [37], [38], [39].

Although Euler angles provide a straightforward approach to representing the tool's rotation, they suffer from gimbal lock singularity. This singularity occurs when the rotation axes for two of the Euler angles become aligned, causing the tool to lose one of its degrees of freedom. In **Figure 1.9**, after the end effector goes through a 90° pitch rotation (**Figure 1.9(b)**) from its resting position (**Figure 1.9(a)**), it can be seen that the roll angle (green ring) aligns with the yaw angle (blue ring). This leads to the loss of the roll rotation of the end effector, effectively reducing its degrees of freedom. As a result, certain orientations become inaccessible or ambiguously represented, complicating tasks such as interpolation, orientation control, and path planning.

In contrast to Euler angles, quaternions offer a compact and robust alternative for representing rotations in three-dimensional space. Comprising four parameters, quaternions bypass the limitations of gimbal lock by representing rotations as mathematical entities in a four-dimensional space [40], [41], [42].

(a) Initial orientation

(b) 90° pitch rotation

Figure 1.9 Gimbal lock phenomenon

Quaternions represent a rotation using a four-dimensional number that encodes both the axis of rotation (r in **Figure 1.10**) and extent of rotation around that axis. The direction or orientation of r is specified by the u (a unit vector along the Cartesian axes (u_x , u_y , and u_z)). For any rotary motion of the end effector through an angle of α (**Figure 1.10(b)**) about its axis of rotation from its initial position (**Figure 1.10(a)**), the resulting quaternion for this rotation is expressed in **Equation 1.12**.

(a) Initial orientation

(b) α rotation about r-axis

Figure 1.10 Quaternion representation

$$\mathbf{Q}_r = \cos\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) + \sin\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) \cdot (u_x i + u_y j + u_z k) \quad 1.12$$

Quaternions also provide an alternative to a HTM by allowing the tool's translation component to be expressed. For every end effector translation \mathbf{t}_p in X (t_x), Y (t_y), and Z (t_z) directions, the equivalent quaternion is expressed in **Equation 1.13**.

$$\mathbf{Q}_t = 0 + \left(\frac{t_x}{2} i + \frac{t_y}{2} j + \frac{t_z}{2} k\right) \quad 1.13$$

By summing up the quaternions for the revolution and sliding of the tool, a dual quaternion (\mathbf{Q}_D), is produced which describes both translation and rotation of the tool and may be substituted for a HTM in FK modelling. **Equation 1.14** represents a dual quaternion where \mathbf{Q}_r is the real part and represents the rotation component, \mathbf{Q}_t is the dual part and represents the translation component, and ϵ is the dual unit satisfying the property $\epsilon^2 = 0$.

$$\mathbf{T}_{End\ effector}^{Base} = \mathbf{Q}_D = \mathbf{Q}_r + \epsilon \mathbf{Q}_t = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) \\ u_x \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) \\ u_y \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) \\ u_z \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) \end{bmatrix} + \epsilon \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{t_x}{2} \\ \frac{t_y}{2} \\ \frac{t_z}{2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{1.14}$$

1.4.2 Differential kinematics

Differential kinematics provides a mathematical model for controlling the robot's speed (both linear and angular), at any given instant. Theoretically, the robot's speed is represented in Cartesian space by differentiating its pose in the FK model (\mathbf{X}), in the FK model (\mathbf{X}) as shown in **Equation 1.15** or in joint space by differentiating the joint angles in the IK model ($\boldsymbol{\theta}$) as shown in **Equation 1.16**. These two equations constitute the velocity kinematics model of the robot.

$$\dot{\mathbf{X}} = \frac{d\mathbf{X}}{dt} \quad \mathbf{1.15}$$

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \frac{d\boldsymbol{\theta}}{dt} = [\dot{\theta}_1, \dot{\theta}_2, \dots, \dot{\theta}_n] \quad \mathbf{1.16}$$

The primary disadvantage of this strategy is that in many circumstances, the position kinematics models (forward and inverse kinematics) are complex and nonlinear. Differentiating them with respect to time can lead to even more complex and nonlinear expressions, which makes analysis and implementation difficult and, in some cases, practically impossible. Furthermore, numerically differentiating complex equations with respect to time can lead to numerical instability, especially when the equations involve trigonometric functions, as is often the case in position kinematics models.

To address these limitations, differential kinematics utilizes the Jacobian matrix, denoted by $J(\theta)$. This matrix contains partial derivatives that describe how minor variations in joint angles affect the pose of the tool. It has $m \times n$ dimensions where m and n are respectively the total elements used to describe the pose of the tool and total joints in the robot. This is indicated in **Equation 1.17**. Where, X_1 to X_3 express the tool's position (t_x, t_y, t_z) , and X_4 to X_n represent the rotation of the tool. When using rotation matrix for orientation representation, n is 12, as there are 3 elements for position representation and 9 elements for orientation. For Euler angle representation, n is 6, as there are 3 elements for orientation (roll, pitch, and yaw), and 3 for position. And for quaternion representation, n is 7, as there are 4 elements for orientation (α, u_x, u_y, u_z) , and 3 elements for position representation.

$$J(\theta) = \frac{\partial X}{\partial \theta} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial X_1}{\partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial X_1}{\partial \theta_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial X_1}{\partial \theta_n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial X_n}{\partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial X_n}{\partial \theta_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial X_n}{\partial \theta_n} \end{bmatrix} \quad 1.17$$

Replacing the direct differentiation with partial derivatives, the speed of the tool in Cartesian space can be determined as shown in **Equation 1.18**. As depicted in **Equation 1.19**, the partial derivatives of the tool's position gives the tool's linear speed (v) in Cartesian space, while the partial derivatives of the orientation components yields angular velocity (ω) in Cartesian space.

$$\dot{X} = J(\theta) \cdot \dot{\theta} \quad 1.18$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} v \\ \omega \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial t_p}{\partial \theta} \\ \frac{\partial R}{\partial \theta} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \dot{\theta} \quad 1.19$$

$$\dot{\theta} = J(\theta)^\dagger \cdot \dot{X} \quad 1.20$$

The pseudoinverse of the Jacobian matrix ($J(\theta)^\dagger$) is calculated and multiplied by the pose of the robot as shown in **Equation 1.20** to determine the tool's speed in joint space. For prismatic joints, the resulting velocity is a linear velocity in joint space, and for revolute joints, the resulting velocity is an angular velocity in joint space.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview

This chapter delves into the methods used in current literature to address both forward and inverse kinematics of industrial robots. After thoroughly examining the existing research, the gaps and limitations of these methods are identified. By identifying these limitations, the objectives of this thesis are formulated to directly address them and propose novel solutions to advance the field of industrial robot kinematics.

There are two primary approaches for tackling robot kinematics: analytical methods and approximate methods. Analytical methods offer closed-form solutions. These solutions are exact, easy to interpret, and are perfectly accurate and reproducible. Although analytical methods are used for solving the IK of robots with simple kinematic structures, they are more typically used for tackling FK, where the relationships between joint parameters and tool positions are straightforward. The Denavit-Hartenberg (DH) convention and Product of Exponentials are common examples of analytical methods used for tackling the FK of robots.

Approximate methods on the other hand trade off some accuracy for computational efficiency and flexibility. This makes them suitable for solving the FK of robots with complex kinematic structures such as exoskeletons and parallel robots. They are also the primary method for dealing with inverse kinematics problems as IK problems are non-linear and can yield multiple solutions, making the application of analytical methods difficult, if not impossible. Iterative methods and machine learning techniques are common examples used for tackling the IK of robots.

2.2 Forward Kinematics Modelling Methods

The various methods used for FK modelling discussed in this section are summarized in **Figure 2.1**.

Figure 2.1 Methods for FK modelling

2.2.1 Analytical methods

The most popular FK modelling method – the Denavit-Hartenberg (DH) convention – relies on a methodical framework to define how the geometry and position of each joint relate to the next. By assigning four distinct parameters (DH parameters), namely joint angle (θ_i), link twist (α_{i-1}), link length (a_{i-1}), and link offset (d_i) to each link systematically and using homogeneous transformation matrices, the tool's pose can be computed efficiently. Out of twenty-four (24) literature reviewed in this thesis, twenty-two (22) employed DH convention to for FK modelling. This shows how ubiquitous the DH convention is in FK modelling. Using the formula in **Equation 2.1**, the HTM for each link (i) is calculated in relation to the preceding link ($i - 1$), beginning from the ground link, down to the tool. The HTMs obtained are then multiplied sequentially from the first link down to the tool. As illustrated in **Equation 2.2**, the sequential operation produces a total HTM which expresses the tool's motion referenced from the ground link.

$$T_i^{i-1} = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta_i & -s\theta_i & 0 & a_{i-1} \\ s\theta_i c\alpha_{i-1} & c\theta_i c\alpha_{i-1} & -s\alpha_{i-1} & -s\alpha_{i-1} d_i \\ s\theta_i s\alpha_{i-1} & c\theta_i s\alpha_{i-1} & c\alpha_{i-1} & c\alpha_{i-1} d_i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad 2.1$$

$$T_{End\ effector}^{Base} = T_1^{Base} \cdot T_2^1 \dots T_{End\ effector}^n \quad 2.2$$

Where, c is cosine, s is sine, $i - 1$ represents the reference link, i represents the link under consideration and n represents the link preceding the end effector.

Product of exponentials (POE), another widely used analytical approach, leverages screw theory and matrix exponentials to formulate a total transformation matrix. While in DH convention DH parameters are assigned to each link, in POE, a 6-dimensional vector (screw vector) is assigned to each joint, describes the instantaneous motion of that joint in terms of translation and rotation relative to the base. **Equation 2.3** represents a screw vector ($\mathbf{S}_i\theta_i$) for any joint i .

$$\mathbf{S}_i\theta_i = \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \\ u_z \\ -(u_y p_z - u_z p_y) \\ -(u_z p_x - u_x p_z) \\ -(u_x p_y - u_y p_x) \end{bmatrix} \theta_i = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_i \\ -\mathbf{u}_i \times \mathbf{p}_i \end{bmatrix} \theta_i \quad 2.3$$

Where θ_i represent joint angle of joint i , \mathbf{u}_i is a 3D vector representing the orientation of the screw axis of the joint i , and \mathbf{p}_i is a 3D position vector from joint i to the base frame. The instantaneous translation of the joint referenced from the ground link is captured by the cross product of the unit direction vector of the rotation axis and the position vector ($-\mathbf{u}_i \times \mathbf{p}_i$), while the instantaneous rotation of the joint is captured by unit direction vector of the rotation axis. Typically, in serial robots, screw vectors are assigned to all joints at resting position of the robot ($\theta = 0$).

Next, the tool's pose is determined relative to the ground link and the resulting transformation matrix, \mathbf{M} is computed at the resting position of the robot. By computing the product of the matrix exponentials of the screw vectors obtained and the transformation matrix, a total transformation matrix describing the tool's pose relative to the ground link is produced as depicted in **Equation 2.4**. POE allows the model to be represented in dual quaternion form as well, by replacing the transformation matrix with its equivalent dual quaternion. This concept is expressed in **Equation 2.5**, where n is the joint preceding the end effector.

$$\mathbf{T}_{End\ effector}^{Base} = \mathbf{M} \cdot e^{S_1\theta_1} \cdot e^{S_2\theta_2} \dots e^{S_n\theta_n} \quad 2.4$$

$$\mathbf{T}_{End\ effector}^{Base} = \mathbf{Q}_D \cdot e^{S_1\theta_1} \cdot e^{S_2\theta_2} \dots e^{S_n\theta_n} \quad 2.5$$

Li et al. [43] compared DH convention-based forward kinematics solutions and product of exponentials-based FK solutions, outlining the pros and cons of using the two approaches. From the findings of this work the DH convention offers simplicity in calculation and versatility but struggles with complex modeling processes, potential singularities, and limitations in representing initial joint positions accurately. POE, however, offers a more extensive and comprehensive way with fewer coordinate systems, overcoming singularities and easing complex mechanism analysis. However, it requires a steeper learning curve and entails cumbersome calculations. Notably, while the DH Parameter Method is more concise in terms of symbols and results, Screw Theory offers a more holistic geometric description.

2.2.2 Machine learning techniques

ML has garnered increased attention in recent times for FK modeling. These methods offer adaptiveness and scalability, especially beneficial for standard robots with numerous degrees of freedom or complex geometries, as well as non-standard robots like exoskeletons. This shift highlights the recognition of deep learning's potential in handling complex FK problems effectively.

Diprasetya et al. [44] introduced the Kinematic Neural Network (KineNN) for learning the DH parameters of a robot manipulator. Two architectures of the KineNN, Homogenous Transformation Matrix (HTMKineNN) and Dual Quaternion (DQKineNN), were proposed to predict tool's pose based on specified joint configurations, integrating DH parameters as learnable parameters. Validation on the Universal Robot 5 demonstrated successful end effector prediction, with DH parameters converging to actual values, except three parameters due to interchangeability.

In their study, Sharkaway et al. [45] introduced an FNN featuring a single hidden layer to compute the FK of a 3-axis articulated robot. The input layer of the FNN received the three joint angles, while the hidden layer consisted of 40 perceptrons. The output layer was designated to generate the 12 parameters that define the end effector's HTM. After training the FNN in 1000 epochs, they achieved successful convergence with a minimal Mean Squared Error (MSE), demonstrating the effectiveness of their model for solving the FK problems in robotics.

2.3 Inverse kinematics Modelling Methods

The inverse kinematics can be broadly categorized into two types: task-free IK and task-specific IK. While task-free IK aims to find all possible joint configurations for any pose within the robot's workspace, task-specific IK, concentrates on solving joint configurations for a particular trajectory or set of connected trajectories within the robot's workspace.

Figure 2.2 IK modelling methods

The various methods used for IK modelling discussed in this section are summarized in **Figure 2.2**.

2.3.1 Task-free inverse kinematics

The two major analytical methods used for IK modelling are geometric methods and algebraic methods. Geometric methods provide a systematic framework for describing a robot's geometry and kinematics, enabling the computation of feasible joint configurations that satisfy given end effector poses [46]. This method involves geometric reasoning and trigonometry. Using established geometric principles and knowledge of the robot's link lengths, it is possible to derive analytical solutions for the joint angles [47].

Algebraic methods manipulate FK model expressed algebraically to represent the relations between joint variables and the tool's pose. This manipulation leverages trigonometry, vector algebra, and matrix algebra to isolate joint variables from equations derived from

the forward kinematics model [48], [49]. By equating these equations to the desired end effector pose, systems are formed and solved to determine the required joint configurations.

Analytical method is particularly suitable for robots with basic kinematic systems, where connections between joint configuration and tool position are capable of being described in closed-form equations. However, for more complex robots with higher degrees of freedom or non-trivial kinematic configurations, iterative techniques may be necessary to address the IK problem effectively.

The core objective of iterative methods is to reduce the difference associated with the desired tool pose and the actual achieved pose by iteratively refining joint angles [50]. As shown in **Figure 2.3**, these methods or algorithms begin with a rough estimate of the robot's joint configuration. Using the FK model, they compute the resulting end effector pose based on this initial guess. This estimated pose is compared to the desired pose, and the margin of error is evaluated. If the margin surpasses a predefined threshold, the joint configuration is modified according to the error value and the Jacobian matrix. This iterative process of pose calculation, error evaluation, and joint angle adjustment continues until the algorithm converges to a joint configuration that positions the tool sufficiently close to the specified goal.

Figure 2.3 Flowchart for IK using iterative methods

Iterative methods for solving the robot IK problem share a common algorithmic foundation. However, they diverge significantly in how they use the Jacobian matrix (**Equation 1.17**) to manipulate pose error to update joint angles (**Equation 2.6**).

$$\Delta \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{J} \Delta \boldsymbol{\theta} \quad 2.6$$

The Jacobian transpose method, introduced by Wolovich et al. [51] and Balestrino et al. [52], is a variant of gradient descent algorithm [53], [54]. Both methods aim to reduce an error function. Here, the function is the error between the tool's current pose (\mathbf{X}_t) and the targeted one ($\mathbf{X}_{desired}$). The learning rate is the step size (α_t) which controls the magnitude of the adjustments made to the joint variables according to the sensitivity captured by the transpose of the Jacobian. The transpose of the Jacobian (\mathbf{J}^T) translates task space changes into the required joint angle adjustments. Each column of this matrix captures how a change along a single axis in the task space affects all joint angles. This sensitivity, which is essentially the slope of the pose error relative to each joint angle, allows multiplication with the desired task space change to provide estimate for the adjustments needed in each joint angle. The primary advantage of using the Jacobian transpose method (gradient descent) is that it eliminates the need for calculating the Jacobian's inverse, greatly simplifying the implementation. Additionally, in certain robotic configurations, the Jacobian matrix can become singular, leading to non-invertibility, or become nearly singular and ill-conditioned. In such cases, attempting to compute the inverse of the matrix can intensify pose errors, causing the algorithm to overshoot the desired pose. These problems are reduced by using the Jacobian transposition approach, which improves the algorithm's robustness and efficiency in difficult optimization scenarios. This method is very also effective in finding global optima (solutions with least pose error). However, because only the direction of steepest descent is captured and the magnitude of change is not well-captured, this algorithm converges slowly compared to inverse Jacobian dependent methods. The slow convergence rate of gradient descent can lead to potentially undershooting the desired pose, especially when the number of iterations is limited.

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\theta}_t = \mathbf{J}_t^T \cdot \alpha (\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_t) \quad 2.7$$

In a robotic system, the Jacobian matrix quantifies the influence of small changes to joint angles on changes in end effector pose. By calculating the pseudo-inverse of the Jacobian, it is possible to determine the required adjustments to the joints to reduce the pose error and attain the targeted tool pose. This concept is implemented in the Gauss-Newton method,

introduced by Baillieul [55], which utilizes the Jacobian's left pseudo-inverse to iteratively refine the initial guess, progressively approaching the target pose as shown in **Equation 2.8**.

$$\Delta\theta_t = (\mathbf{J}_t^T \cdot \mathbf{J}_t)^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{J}_t^T \cdot \alpha(\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_t) \quad 2.8$$

This method is ideal when the Jacobian is well-conditioned due to its inherent speed of convergence. It however fails to converge or may produce erroneous results in or near singular regions. Farzan et al. [48] proposed a fast and robust variant of the previous method, employing the Moore-Penrose (MP) generalized inverse (J^{-P}) rather than the left pseudo-inverse. The MP inverse of the Jacobian is derived from its SVD (Singular Value Decomposition) [56], [57], [58]. The SVD represents the Jacobian matrix as the product of three matrices: \mathbf{U} , \mathbf{S} , and \mathbf{V}^T , where \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} are orthogonal matrices respectively representing the left and right singular vectors of \mathbf{J} . The singular values of \mathbf{J} are contained in the diagonal matrix, \mathbf{S} . The MP inverse of the of the Jacobian is given by:

$$\mathbf{J}^{-P} = \mathbf{V} \cdot \mathbf{S}^{-P} \cdot \mathbf{U}^T \quad 2.9$$

By utilizing the SVD, the MP pseudoinverse in **Equation 2.10** provides a method for effectively computing the inverse of non-square matrices and handling singular or ill-conditioned matrices. Thus, this method provides both robustness and speed.

$$\Delta\theta_t = \mathbf{J}_t^{-P} * \alpha(\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_t) \quad 2.10$$

Nakamura [59] and Wampler [60] introduced the Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) approach, which is often referred to as the damped least squares (DLS) method. LM combines features from the first two aforementioned methods. When the damping factor approaches zero, LM behaves like Gauss-Newton, prioritizing the inverse Jacobian for updates. This can lead to faster convergence but potentially less stability. Conversely with increasing values of the damping factor, LM behaves like gradient descent, prioritizing the transpose of the Jacobian for updates. This can lead to slower convergence but potentially more stable behaviour, as the damping term effectively controls the step size and mitigates the effects of ill-conditioned and singular Jacobian matrices. The expression for its joint angle adjustment is given below:

$$\Delta\theta_t = (\mathbf{J}_t^T \cdot \mathbf{J}_t + \lambda I)^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{J}_t^T \cdot \alpha(\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_t) \quad 2.11$$

Below is a proposed pseudo code for the implementation of LM method by Larsson et al. [61] for IK:

Algorithm 1 Inverse Jacobian solver based on LM optimization [61]

$\mathbf{X}_{desired}$			▷ Input the desired pose
$\boldsymbol{\theta}_{current}$			▷ Input the initial joint angles
α			▷ Input the desired step size
tolerance			▷ Input the desired tolerance
λ			▷ Input the desired damping factor
while $ \mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_t \geq \text{tolerance}$ do			▷ Repeat till tolerance is reached
$\mathbf{J} = \text{Jacobian}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t)$			▷ Compute the Jacobian w.r.t to current joint angles
$\mathbf{J_inv} = (\mathbf{J}_t^T * \mathbf{J}_t + \lambda * \mathbf{I})^{-1} * \mathbf{J}_t^T$			▷ Compute inverse of the Jacobian
$\Delta\boldsymbol{\theta}_t = \mathbf{J_inv} * \alpha * \mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_t $			▷ Compute joint angle adjustment
$\boldsymbol{\theta}_t = \boldsymbol{\theta}_t + \Delta\boldsymbol{\theta}$			▷ Update joint angle
$\boldsymbol{\theta}_t = \text{joint_limits}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t)$			▷ Regulate to limit if more/less than limit
$\mathbf{X}_t = \text{ForwardKinematics}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t)$			▷ Calculate tool pose
end while			

The general limitation of iterative methods is that they can exhibit slow convergence, especially for robots with complex kinematic structures. This limitation increases computation time and can potentially lead to divergence. Additionally, these methods can struggle with singularities, where the Jacobian becomes singular, significantly hindering the algorithm's ability to determine proper joint adjustments and ultimately leading to non-convergence. This work introduces a novel adaptive Levenberg-Marquardt (ALM) algorithm for robot inverse kinematics with the objective to overcome these drawbacks. This algorithm leverages the LM framework but incorporates dynamic adjustments to the damping factor and step size in each iteration to enhance convergence speed, robustness and pose accuracy, particularly in both simple and challenging scenarios.

Xiao et al. [62] proposed a hybrid optimization, combining LM optimization and momentum item, for training backpropagation neural networks (BPNNs). Their method incorporated dynamic adjustments of the momentum coefficient (α_t) and damping factor (λ_t). The core concept is to dynamically adjust the momentum coefficient (α_t) and damping factor (λ_t) based on the error term's behaviour. When the error term decreases, it indicates effective weight updates. In this case, α_t is increased to leverage this momentum and potentially accelerate convergence. Conversely, if the error term increases, α_t is decreased to introduce more cautious updates and improve stability. To prevent α_t from exceeding the

valid range (0, 1), any adjustments that push it above one are capped at 0.01. The damping factor (λ_t) behaves differently. It increases with a rising error term, making the algorithm resemble Gauss-Newton for potentially faster convergence. However, when the error term decreases, λ_t is reduced, shifting the behaviour towards gradient descent for enhanced stability and the ability to find global minima. The specific update rules are presented below:

$$\alpha_t = \begin{cases} 1.2\alpha_{t-1}, & E(t) < E(t-1) \\ \alpha_{t-1}, & E(t) = E(t-1) \\ \alpha_{t-1}/1.2, & E(t) > E(t-1) \\ 0.01, & \alpha_t > 1 \end{cases} \quad 2.12$$

$$\lambda_t = \begin{cases} 1.2\lambda_{t-1}, & E(t) > E(t-1) \\ \lambda_{t-1}, & E(t) = E(t-1) \\ \lambda_{t-1}/1.2, & E(t) < E(t-1) \end{cases} \quad 2.13$$

This study merges a modification Xiao et al.'s proposal and the standard LM algorithm proposed by Larsson et al., aiming to develop an adaptive LM algorithm suitable for task-free industrial robot inverse kinematics.

2.3.2 Task-specific inverse kinematics

IK problems have traditionally been solved using numerical (iterative) approaches (task-free and task-specific), offering high accuracy but often at the cost of computational speed. This is why ML models are gaining traction as an alternative approach [50], [63]. ML models, when trained, can approximate IK solutions much faster than numerical methods [64]. Additionally, their simple structure allows for easy integration into robot control systems. This translates to real-time computation of IK solutions, making ML models valuable tools for modern robotics applications [13], [65], [66], [67]. Despite their speed advantage, ML models may not always achieve the high accuracy and precision required for industrial applications, especially for complex tasks, and training them can also be time-consuming. Highlighting the accuracy limitation, a study by Demby et al. [68] found that ML models are not well-suited for task-free IK problems, where achieving high accuracy for every possible pose is crucial. Even for task-specific problems, ML models may struggle to achieve the sub-millimeter positional accuracy and sub-degree/sub-radian orientation accuracy required for industrial applications. To address this, researchers like Almusawi et al. [69] and Sherbiny et al. [64] have explored hybrid approaches combining

ML models with iterative methods. While these hybrids offer improved accuracy, they come at the cost of increased computation times, making them unsuitable for real-time applications.

Recent advancements in FNN modelling offer promising results for industrial applications. Models developed by Tagliani et al. [63] and Sharkawy et al. [45] achieved very low Mean Squared Errors (MSEs) of $1.74 \times 10^{-6} \text{ rad}^2$ and $9.07 \times 10^{-7} \text{ rad}^2$ respectively. While these MSEs are not as low as hybrid approaches such as Almusawi et al.'s [69] ($3.3029 \times 10^{-8} \text{ rad}^2$), the recent developments suggest that FNNs can be further optimized to achieve industrial-grade accuracy while maintaining their real-time processing advantage. Secondly, this research seeks to leverage recent advancements in FNN modelling to develop a novel trajectory planning model for industrial robots. The primary objective is to reduce training time while maintaining high accuracy and precision in predicting Cartesian poses, thereby addressing a critical limitation of existing FNN-based approaches for industrial applications.

2.4 Summary of Literature Review

Table 2.1 is a summary of the literature reviewed in this thesis, the approaches used for FK and IK modelling, the DOF of the robots used in kinematics analysis, and their major contribution. The year of publication of the selected literature span from 2016 to 2023.

Table 2.1 Summary of Relevant Literature

SN	Ref.	Year	FK modelling method(s)	IK modelling method(s)	DOF of robot(s)	Contribution
1	[70]	2016	DH	Geometric	5	Designed a robotic arm to assist elderly or specially challenged individuals with feeding tasks
2	[64]	2017	DH	FNN, ANFIS, GA	5	Comparative analysis of FNN, ANFIS and GA for inverse kinematics modelling Proposed an optimization algorithm to increase the

						performance of ANFIS and FNN for IK modelling
3	[71]	2018	DH	Geometric	3	Automatic control of robotic arm using PID controller
4	[72]	2018	DH	Algebraic, ANFIS	5	Kinematics modelling of robot using analytical methods and ANFIS
5	[73]	2018	DH	Algebraic	3	Optimization of the cross-sectional shape of robot links to attain maximum structural strength relative to weight Kinematics modelling of robot using analytical methods
6	[74]	2019	—————	Geometric	3	Design of robotic arm for automation of crop harvesting tasks.
7	[75]	2020	DH	Algebraic, FNN	5	Kinematics modelling of robot using analytical methods and FNN
8	[76]	2020	DH	FNN, CNN	7	Proposed a CNN-FNN hybrid architecture for IK of robot Comparative analysis of hybrid architecture and conventional FNN for IK of robot
9	[77]	2020	DH	MP, UC, and MX techniques, FNN, ANFIS	3, 4, 5, 6, 7	Proposed MX inverse numerical solution for IK of robot Comparative analysis of FNN, ANFIS, and three numerical methods for IK of robot
10	[43]	2021	DH, POE	—————	7	Comparative analysis of DH convention and POE formula for robot FK modelling
11	[4]	2021	DH	Algebraic	6	Kinematics modelling of robot arm using kinematic

						decoupling and algebraic method
12	[78]	2021	DH	FNN	4	Proposed an FOA optimized FNN for IK of robot Addressed the limitations of low convergence accuracy and speed, as well as susceptibility to getting stuck in local minima points commonly associated with FNN for IK of robot
13	[79]	2021	DH	FNN	6	Kinematics modelling of robot using an analytical method and FNN
14	[49]	2021	DH	Algebraic, Geometric	3	Kinematics modelling of robot using analytical methods
15	[80]	2021	DH	ANFIS	6	Proposed a hybrid method (ANFIS and Newton-Raphson algorithm) for IK of robot
16	[63]	2022	DH	FNN	6	Proposed a sequential FNN approach with neural structure optimized by GA for IK modelling
18	[81]	2022	DH	Geometric	6	Kinematics modelling of robot using analytical methods
19	[66]	2022	POE	DQN	7	Kinematics modelling of robot using an analytical method and RL
20	[82]	2022	DH, RL	FNN	7	Proposed a RL algorithm for FK modelling and FNN for IK modelling
21	[83]	2022	DH	ANFIS	5	Developed a model of merged multiple ANFIS (MANFIS) for IK of robot
22	[44]	2023	DH, FNN, DQKineNN, HTMKineNN	DQKineNN, HTMKineNN	6	Proposed two kinematics neural networks for kinematics modelling of robot
23	[45]	2023	DH, FNN	Algebraic, FNN	3	Proposed a FNN for kinematics modelling of robot

24	[61]	2023	DH	Jacobian transpose, Gauss-Newton, LM	6	Proposed 3 algorithms based on iterative methods for IK
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2.5 Research Objectives

- Develop a novel adaptive Levenberg-Marquardt (ALM) algorithm for task-free inverse kinematics with enhanced convergence speed, robustness, pose accuracy, and pose precision, for both simple poses and complex poses with potential singularities.
- Prepare a comprehensive dataset of robot poses and corresponding joint configurations (using the ALM algorithm) for the training of an FNN model for task-specific inverse kinematics
- Develop an FNN model for trajectory planning in task-specific inverse kinematics with a short training time, improved accuracy and precision, and higher potential of enhancing real-world trajectory execution.

3. METHODOLOGY AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

3.1 Overview

This thesis tackles two robot inverse kinematics problems: task-free inverse kinematics and task-specific inverse kinematics. For task-free IK, this thesis presents a novel adaptive Levenberg-Marquardt (ALM) algorithm designed to enhance convergence speed, robustness, pose accuracy, and pose precision, for both simple poses and complex poses with potential singularities. For task-specific IK, the thesis introduces a Feedforward Neural Network (FNN) model leveraging recent advancements in neural network modeling to achieve short training time, improved accuracy and precision, and a higher potential of enhancing real-world trajectory execution.

The effectiveness of both the ALM and FNN methodologies are evaluated by applying them to ABB IRB 6700 robot model. The ABB IRB 6700 model (**Figure 3.1**) features a carrying capacity of 150 to 300 kg and a reach of 2.6 to 3.2 meters, thus being ideal for a range of uses in industries [84].

Figure 3.1. ABB IRB 6700 CAD model

There are three primary subsections in this chapter. The initial subsection details the forward kinematics of the ABB IRB 6700 robot. This includes the mathematical modeling and derivation of the FK equations. The second subsection describes the development and implementation of the ALM algorithm for task-free IK, and the third subsection details the methodology for developing the FNN model for task-specific IK.

3.2 Forward Kinematics

The forward kinematics of the ABB IRB 6700 industrial robot is modelled using the robot's DH parameters. The last column of the DH parameter table (**Table 3.1**) also contains the range of motion (ROM) for each of the six joints of the ABB IRB 6700. This information is directly sourced from the manufacturer's product specifications [85], ensuring compatibility and accuracy when modelling the robot's movements.

Table 3.1 DH Parameter Table

Link (i)	Joint angle ($\theta_i/^\circ$)	Link offset (d_i/m)	Link length (a_{i-1}/m)	Link twist ($\alpha_{i-1}/^\circ$)	Range of motion ($\theta_{imin}:\theta_{imax}/^\circ$)
1	θ_1	0.78	0	0	-170:+170
2	θ_2	0	0.32	90	-65:+85
3	θ_3	0	1.28	0	-180:+70
4	θ_4	1.5925	0.2	90	-300:+300
5	θ_5	0	0	-90	-130:+130
6	θ_6	0.71113	0	90	-360:+360

Using the DH parameter table and **Equation 2.1**, the pose of each link (i) with respect to its previous adjacent link (i-1) is determined. The poses for the links with reference to their previous adjacent links are provided in **Equations 3.1** to **3.6** below.

$$T_1^0 = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 & -s_1 & 0 & 0 \\ s_1 & c_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0.78 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{3.1}$$

$$T_2^1 = \begin{bmatrix} c_2 & -s_2 & 0 & 0.32 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ s_2 & c_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{3.2}$$

$$T_3^2 = \begin{bmatrix} c_3 & -s_3 & 0 & 1.28 \\ s_3 & c_3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad 3.3$$

$$T_4^3 = \begin{bmatrix} c_4 & -s_4 & 0 & 0.2 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & -1.5925 \\ s_4 & c_4 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad 3.4$$

$$T_5^4 = \begin{bmatrix} c_5 & -s_5 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s_5 & -c_5 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad 3.5$$

$$T_6^5 = \begin{bmatrix} c_6 & -s_6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & -0.71113 \\ s_6 & c_6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad 3.6$$

The forward kinematics for the ABB IRB 6700 robot is obtained by sequentially multiplying **Equations 3.1** to **3.6** to obtain a total HTM that describes the tool's pose referenced from the ground link as given in **Equation 2.2**. The elements of the HTM are provided in **Equations 3.10** to **3.21**, with the first nine (9) equations describing the orientation and the last three (3) describing position. The rotation matrix representation is converted to Euler angle representation. Employing the ZYX convention, roll (φ) is designated for rotation about the Z-axis ($R_z(\varphi)$), pitch (θ_e) about the Y-axis ($R_y(\theta_e)$), and yaw (ψ) about the X-axis ($R_x(\psi)$). This is provided in **Equations 3.22** to **3.24**. Similarly, the rotation matrix representation can be converted to quaternion representation using the four conditions and **Equations 3.26** to **3.45**

$$T_6^0 = T_1^0 \cdot T_2^1 \cdot T_3^2 \cdot T_4^3 \cdot T_5^4 \cdot T_6^5 \quad 3.7$$

$$T_6^0 = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 & -s_1 & 0 & 0 \\ s_1 & c_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0.78 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} c_2 & -s_2 & 0 & 0.32 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ s_2 & c_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} c_3 & -s_3 & 0 & 1.28 \\ s_3 & c_3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} c_4 & -s_4 & 0 & 0.2 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & -1.5925 \\ s_4 & c_4 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} c_5 & -s_5 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s_5 & -c_5 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} c_6 & -s_6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & -0.71113 \\ s_6 & c_6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad 3.8$$

$$T_6^0 = \begin{bmatrix} r_{xx} & r_{yx} & r_{zx} & t_x \\ r_{xy} & r_{yy} & r_{zy} & t_y \\ r_{xz} & r_{yz} & r_{zz} & t_z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad 3.9$$

$$r_{xx} = s_6(c_4s_1 - c_1c_{23}s_4) + c_6(c_5(s_1s_4 + c_1c_{23}c_4) - c_1s_{23}s_5) \quad 3.10$$

$$r_{xy} = -s_6(c_1c_4 - c_{23}s_1s_4) - c_6(c_5(c_1s_4 - c_{23}c_4s_1) + s_1s_{23}s_5) \quad 3.11$$

$$r_{xz} = c_6(c_{23}s_5 + s_{23}c_4c_5) - s_{23}s_4s_6 \quad 3.12$$

$$r_{yx} = c_6(c_4s_1 - c_1c_{23}s_4) - s_6(c_5(s_1s_4 + c_1c_{23}c_4) - c_1s_{23}s_5) \quad 3.13$$

$$r_{yy} = -c_6(c_1c_4 - c_{23}s_1s_4) + s_6(c_5(c_1s_4 - c_{23}c_4s_1) + s_1s_5s_{23}) \quad 3.14$$

$$r_{yz} = -s_6(c_{23}s_5 + s_{23}c_4c_5) - s_{23}c_6s_4 \quad 3.15$$

$$r_{zx} = s_5(s_1s_4 + c_1c_{23}c_4) - s_{23}c_6s_4 \quad 3.16$$

$$r_{zy} = c_5s_1s_{23} - s_5(c_1s_4 - c_{23}c_4s_1) \quad 3.17$$

$$r_{zz} = c_4s_{23}s_5 - c_{23}c_5 \quad 3.18$$

$$t_x = 0.32c_1 + 1.28c_1c_2 + 0.71113s_5(s_1s_4 + c_1c_4c_{23}) + 0.71113s_{23}c_1c_5 + 0.2c_1c_{23} + 1.5925c_1s_{23} \quad 3.19$$

$$t_y = 0.32s_1 + 1.28c_2s_1 - 0.71113s_5(c_1s_4 - c_4s_1c_{23}) + 0.71113s_{23}c_5s_1 + 0.2s_1c_{23} + 1.5925s_1s_{23} \quad 3.20$$

$$t_z = 0.2s_{23} - 1.5925c_{23} + 1.28s_2 + 0.71113c_4s_{23}s_5 - 0.71113c_{23}c_5 + 0.78 \quad 3.21$$

$$\theta_e = \text{atan2}(-r_{xz}, \sqrt{1 - r_{xz}^2}) \quad 3.22$$

$$\varphi = \text{atan2}\left(\frac{r_{xz}}{\cos(\theta_e)}, \frac{r_{yy}}{\cos(\theta_e)}\right) \quad 3.23$$

$$\psi = \text{atan2}\left(\frac{r_{yz}}{\cos(\theta_e)}, \frac{r_{zz}}{\cos(\theta_e)}\right) \quad 3.24$$

$$\text{tr}(T_6^0) = r_{xx} + r_{yy} + r_{zz} \quad 3.25$$

Condition 1: If $\text{tr}(T_6^0) > 0$:

$$S = 2 \times \sqrt{\text{tr}(T_6^0) + 1} \quad 3.26$$

$$q_w = \frac{S}{4} \quad 3.27$$

$$q_x = \frac{r_{yz} - r_{zy}}{S} \quad 3.28$$

$$q_y = \frac{r_{zx} - r_{xz}}{S} \quad 3.29$$

$$q_z = \frac{r_{xy} - r_{yx}}{S} \quad 3.30$$

Condition 2: If $(r_{xx} > r_{yy})$ and $(r_{xx} > r_{zz})$:

$$S = 2 \times \sqrt{1 + r_{xx} - r_{yy} - r_{zz}} \quad 3.31$$

$$q_w = \frac{r_{yz} - r_{zy}}{S} \quad 3.32$$

$$q_x = \frac{S}{4} \quad 3.33$$

$$q_y = \frac{r_{xy} + r_{yx}}{S} \quad 3.34$$

$$q_z = \frac{r_{zx} + r_{xz}}{S} \quad 3.35$$

Condition 3: If $r_{yy} > r_{zz}$:

$$S = 2 \times \sqrt{1 + r_{yy} - r_{xx} - r_{zz}} \quad 3.36$$

$$q_w = \frac{r_{zx} - r_{xz}}{S} \quad 3.37$$

$$q_x = \frac{r_{xy} + r_{yx}}{S} \quad 3.38$$

$$q_y = \frac{S}{4} \quad 3.39$$

$$q_z = \frac{r_{yz} + r_{zy}}{S} \quad 3.40$$

Condition 4: Else:

$$S = 2 \times \sqrt{1 + r_{zz} - r_{xx} - r_{yy}} \quad 3.41$$

$$q_w = \frac{r_{xy} - r_{yx}}{S} \quad 3.42$$

$$q_x = \frac{r_{zx} + r_{xz}}{S} \quad 3.43$$

$$q_y = \frac{r_{yz} + r_{zy}}{s} \quad 3.44$$

$$q_z = \frac{s}{4} \quad 3.45$$

3.3 Novel Adaptive LM for Task-free IK

To evaluate the robustness of the proposed algorithm, four distinct robot poses are generated using the FK. Poses 1 and 2 were deliberately chosen to be far from singular configurations, while Poses 3 and 4 were selected to be near singularities. This approach allows the assessment of the algorithm's performance under both favorable and challenging kinematic conditions. **Table 3.2** depicts the input joint configurations for each pose and the resulting tool pose derived from the FK model. The Cartesian position of the tool is in meters. The tool's rotation is specified in degrees using the ZYX Euler angle convention.

Table 3.2. Joint Configurations and Resulting End Effector Poses

Pose	Joint configuration ($\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4, \theta_5, \theta_6$)	End effector pose ($x, y, z, \varphi, \theta_e, \psi$)
1	(30, 120, -30, 30, 30, 30)	(1.7243, 0.7902, 2.3964, -88.1868, -23.5481, -61.8132)
2	(-40, 40, 50, -60, -60, -60)	(2.1457, -2.4967, 1.4948, 16.3099, 38.6822, 123.6901)
3	(-160, 30, 110, -280, -120, -330)	(-1.8151, -1.3061, 2.4274, -139.6758, -12.1042, -119.3796)
4	(120 140 -50 250 100 320)	(-0.9742, 0.3711, 1.5632, -35.4344, 33.9540, 113.9578)

The four poses are simulated within a CAD software. A virtual wooden slab is positioned at the poses generated by the FK model for four specific sets of joint angles. This step accounts for slight differences in joint angles between the FK model and the CAD model itself. Specifically, the CAD model's second joint angle (θ_2) is offset by 90 degrees, with a resulting ROM of +25 to +175 degrees. Additionally, the third joint angle in the CAD model has a reversed motion ($-\theta_3$), leading to an ROM of +180 to -70 degrees. The results of the simulation is shown in **Figure 3.2** below:

(a) Pose 1

(b) Pose 2

(c) Pose 3

(d) Pose 4

Figure 3.2. Simulation of four poses

The existing adaptive LM method [62] introduced for training of BPPNs is leveraged here with slight modifications for the purpose of inverse kinematics (IK) solving. In this adaptation, the momentum coefficient is treated as the step size which also ranges from 0 to 1 [77]. The error term (pose error), which guides the update direction, is defined as the difference between the desired pose ($\mathbf{X}_{desired}$) and the pose at each iteration (\mathbf{X}_t). The update rule is the primary distinction of the proposed ALM algorithm from the existing one. The proposed method first sets a maximum and minimum threshold for the for the step size (α_{max} and α_{min}) and damping factor ($\lambda_{min}, \lambda_{max}$). If the error decreases, indicating progress, the step size is cautiously increased by a factor of 1.2, up to a maximum limit of α_{max} , and the damping factor concurrently decreased by the same factor, with a minimum limit of λ_{min} . Conversely, if the error increases, the step size is conservatively reduced by a factor of 1.2, with a minimum limit of α_{min} and the damping factor concurrently increased by the same factor, with a maximum limit of λ_{max} . Setting these limits help the algorithm find the optimal solution efficiently while avoiding large updates that could lead it astray. The update rules for the proposed algorithm are as follows:

$$\alpha_t = \begin{cases} \min(\alpha_{max}, 1.2\alpha_{t-1}), & |\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_t| < |\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_{t-1}| \\ \alpha_{t-1}, & |\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_t| = |\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_{t-1}| \\ \max(\alpha_{min}, \alpha_{t-1}/1.2), & |\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_t| > |\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_{t-1}| \end{cases} \quad 3.46$$

$$\lambda_t = \begin{cases} \min(\lambda_{max}, 1.2\lambda_{t-1}), & |\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_t| > |\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_{t-1}| \\ \lambda_{t-1}, & |\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_t| = |\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_{t-1}| \\ \max(\lambda_{min}, \lambda_{t-1}/1.2), & |\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_t| < |\mathbf{X}_{desired} - \mathbf{X}_{t-1}| \end{cases} \quad 3.47$$

The pseudo code for the proposed algorithm is given below. The values of α_{min} and α_{max} are 0 and 1 respectively, and the values of λ_{min} and λ_{max} are 0 and 100 respectively. The pseudo code outlining the implementation of the proposed method for solving inverse kinematics is provided below:

Algorithm 2 Proposed ALM algorithm

```
Xdesired           ▷ Input the desired pose
θt                 ▷ Input the initial joint angles
αt                 ▷ Input the desired initial step size
αmax              ▷ Input the desired maximum step size
αmin              ▷ Input the desired minimum step size
λt                 ▷ Input the desired initial damping factor
λmax              ▷ Input the desired maximum damping factor
λmin              ▷ Input the desired minimum damping factor
tolerance           ▷ Input the desired tolerance
while |Xdesired - Xt| >= tolerance do           ▷ Repeat till tolerance is reached
  J = Jacobian(θt)           ▷ Compute the Jacobian w.r.t to current joint angles
  Jinv = (JtT * Jt + λt * I)-1 * JtT           ▷ Compute inverse of the Jacobian
  Δθt = Jinv * αt * |Xdesired - Xt|           ▷ Compute joint angle adjustment
  θt = θt + Δθ           ▷ Update joint angle
  θt = joint_limits(θt)           ▷ Adjust to max/min value if above/under limit
  Xt = ForwardKinematics(θt)           ▷ Compute pose with FK model
  λt = f(λ)           ▷ Compute adaptive damping factor
  αt = f(α)           ▷ Compute adaptive step size
end while
```

3.4 FNN Modelling for Task-Specific IK

The modelling of the FNN takes place in three comprehensive steps as outlined in **Figure 3.3**. In the first step the experimental Cartesian space trajectory is generated within the joint limits of the robot. In the second step, a dataset comprising of the robot poses and corresponding joint configurations for the planned trajectory is prepared. These joint configurations are obtained using the proposed ALM algorithm. In the final step, an FNN model is trained on the prepared dataset to solve the task-specific IK problem.

Figure 3.3. Workflow of research

3.4.1 Trajectory Generation

The Cartesian space trajectory planning process begins with the selection of five waypoints within the robot's workspace to outline the path the tool would follow. To smoothly connect these waypoints, linear interpolation is employed for the position coordinates of each point. The resulting plot of the trajectory is shown in **Figure 3.4**.

Figure 3.4. Robot trajectory in Cartesian space

For orientation, quaternions are used to completely represent each waypoint's pose. This avoids the gimbal lock issue inherent to Euler angles and offers a more concise representation of 3D rotations. Spherical Linear Interpolation (SLERP) is then employed to interpolate smoothly between the quaternion representations, ensuring a continuous and realistic path for the robot's tool throughout the entire trajectory. The result is shown in **Figure 3.5**. However, after trajectory generation, the quaternions are changed to Euler angles (ZYX convention). **Figure 3.6** highlights this.

Figure 3.5. SLERP interpolation trajectory between quaternions

Figure 3.6. Trajectories of Euler angles

3.4.2 Dataset Preparation

For each consecutive pair of waypoints on the trajectory generated, there are 4,000 intermediate poses between them, resulting in a total trajectory of 20,000 datapoints. The dataset preparation stage provides the corresponding joint configurations for all the 20,000 poses in the trajectory. 80% (16,000) of the total datapoints are allocated for training the model, while the remaining 20% (4,000) is allocated as testing data. The joint space trajectories for the poses are shown in **Figure 3.7**.

Figure 3.7. Joint space trajectories

3.4.3 FNN Model Design and Training

This section details the design and training of the FNN model. The network tackles a straightforward regression task: predicting the 6 robot joint angles for each pose in the

trajectory. The Neural Network Toolbox in MATLAB offers the ‘fitnet’ function specifically designed for creating and training user-friendly FNNs for regression tasks. It builds upon the more fundamental ‘feedforwardnet’ function but provides a higher level of abstraction, simplifying the process. The FNN architecture employs ‘fitnet’ and features a 3-layer stack of hidden layers, each containing 10 neurons. This is preceded by an input layer and finalized with an output layer. The two layers are sized according to the dimensions of the input features (poses) and target labels (joint angles), respectively. The FNN’s architecture is shown in **Figure 3.8**.

Figure 3.8. Architecture of Feedforward Neural Network

The following are the activation functions chosen for the network’s layers optimize performance: the ‘tansig’ (hyperbolic tangent sigmoid) transfer function is chosen for the hidden layers use, since it introduces non-linearity and enables the network to learn complex patterns, and the ‘purelin’ (linear) transfer function is chosen for the output layer, as it is appropriate for regression tasks, maintaining a linear relationship with the target variable. The entire network is trained using Bayesian regularization, a robust optimizer that adjusts the network’s complexity to prevent overfitting. As Bayesian regularization inherently controls overfitting, no additional regularizer is applied. Mean Squared Error (MSE) serves as the error function. Minimizing MSE guides the training process towards better accuracy. Finally, the training is expected to iterate for 1000 epochs, ensuring adequate learning and convergence.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Novel Adaptive LM for Task-free IK

This section evaluates the performance of the proposed Adaptive Levenberg-Marquardt (ALM) method against the existing ALM and standard (non-adaptive) LM methods. The evaluation considers four key metrics: convergence rate, accuracy, precision, convergence speed (measured by number of iterations), and computational efficiency (measured by computation time). To ensure a fair comparison, 1,000 sets of random initial damping factors and step sizes were used as input parameters for all three algorithms across four different poses. A maximum iteration limit of 1,000 was set for each test run. The experiments were conducted on a 2.10 GHz Intel Core i3 CPU.

Table 4.1. Comparison Table for Convergence Rate

Pose		Convergence count	Divergence count	Convergence rate (%)
1	Standard LM	253	747	25.3
	Existing ALM	1000	0	100
	Proposed ALM	1000	0	100
2	Standard LM	249	751	24.9
	Existing ALM	1000	0	100
	Proposed ALM	1000	0	100
3	Standard LM	162	838	16.2
	Existing ALM	704	296	70.4
	Proposed ALM	703	297	70.3
4	Standard LM	35	965	3.5
	Existing ALM	840	319	84.0
	Proposed ALM	848	152	84.8

Figure 4.1. Comparison of convergence

Analysis of **Table 4.1** and **Figure 4.1** reveals that the two adaptive LM algorithms achieve very high convergence rate, demonstrating superior robustness in finding IK solutions, with no significant difference between the convergence rate, and hence robustness, of the proposed adaptive LM algorithm and the existing adaptive LM algorithm.

The following analysis will exclusively consider data points where all three algorithms converged for each of the four poses. In other words, any instances where an algorithm failed to converge for a specific pose are excluded. The pose error and computational efficiency is then analysed using the filtered dataset. **Table 4.2** and **Figure 4.2** reveal that the proposed adaptive LM algorithm consistently achieves the lowest median pose errors across all four poses (1.471×10^{-15} , 1.349×10^{-15} , 1.250×10^{-15} , 1.013×10^{-15}), demonstrating superior accuracy in solving IK problems compared to the existing ALM algorithm, even achieving 100% accuracy in few instances. Figure 4.2 also reveals that the proposed algorithm maintains superior precision (smaller interquartile range) even in near-singular configurations (poses 3 and 4). This suggests more consistent performance compared to the existing adaptive LM algorithm, which exhibits increased imprecision when approaching singularities.

Table 4.2. Comparison Table for Accuracy and Computational Efficiency

Pose		Pose error ($\times 10^{-15}$)			Number of iterations			Computation (ms)		
		Max	Min	Median	Max	Min	Median	Max	Min	Median
1	SLM	10.00	0.828	9.177	115	81	102.0	13	0.13	1.37
	EALM	9.987	0.339	4.335	8874	122	304.0	142	1.11	4.02
	PALM	9.850	0	1.471	58	8	27.00	14.2	0.07	0.34
2	SLM	10.00	1.439	9.383	1040	10	176.0	13.9	0.16	1.85
	EALM	9.982	3.896	2.945	116	83	104.0	98.7	0.73	0.98
	PALM	9.994	0.202	1.349	2622	11	27.00	41.3	0.11	0.34
3	SLM	9.981	1.335	9.054	639	23	155.0	9.27	0.21	1.76
	EALM	9.967	0.254	4.534	1845	86	289.0	110	1.35	3.63
	PALM	9.939	0.169	1.250	52	13	26.00	29.1	0.14	0.30
4	SLM	9.950	0.624	5.738	142	15	44.00	2.59	0.17	0.49
	EALM	9.997	0.561	4.511	8895	87	147.5	18.9	1.39	1.07
	PALM	9.927	0.208	1.013	7415	10	56.50	29.1	0.10	0.62

Figure 4.2. Comparison of pose error

Figure 4.3. Comparison of convergence speed

Figure 4.4. Comparison of computational efficiency

Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4, and Table 4.2 reveal that the proposed adaptive LM algorithm achieves the lowest median number of iterations (27, 27, 26) and lowest median computation times (0.34, 0.34, 0.3) across the first three poses, demonstrating superior

speed in converging to IK solutions as well as superior computational efficiency. In pose 4 however, the standard LM algorithm achieved a slightly lower median number of iterations (44) and computation time (0.49 ms), compared to the proposed algorithm's median number of iterations (56.5 ms) and its computation time (0.62 ms). This can be attributed to the standard LM algorithm's low convergence rate (35 out of 1000) in pose 4. This suggests that these few instances where there was convergence are scenarios where it could achieve convergence relatively quickly, resulting in a lower median number of iterations and computation time compared to the proposed algorithm. However, as its convergence rate increases as seen in the other poses, its speed of convergence will be significantly less than the proposed algorithm.

4.2 FNN Modelling for Task-Specific IK

An evaluation of the model's performance on the regression task is completed in this section. This evaluation is centered around three key metrics: Mean Error (ME), Standard Deviation (STD), and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). ME quantifies the accuracy of the model, while STD measures its precision. The formulation for ME and STD are provided in **Equations 4.2** and **4.3** respectively. RMSE combines the two metrics to give a thorough assessment of how the model performs in general. Its formulation is provided in **Equation 4.1**.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Real_i - Predicted_i)^2} \quad 4.1$$

$$ME = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n Real_i - Predicted_i \quad 4.2$$

$$STD = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n ([Real_i - Predicted_i] - mean[Real - Predicted])^2} \quad 4.3$$

Finally, a feasibility analysis is conducted by comparing the STD values of the robot's positions throughout the trajectory with the path repeatability (RT) of the ABB IRB 6700. Path repeatability is a performance metric defined by ISO 9283, which measures the ability of a robot to return to a predefined position repeatedly with minimal deviation [86]. According to ISO tests performed on several variants of the IRB 6700, the lowest RT

recorded was 0.07 mm for the 300/2.70 variant [85]. The average of the STD values of the robot's positions throughout the trajectory with this 0.07 mm value. This comparative analysis helps determine if the model's predictions are sufficiently aligned with the robot's physical capabilities to achieve highly precise and reliable performance in real-world operations.

As depicted in **Figure 4.5**, the training and testing losses are analyzed using MSE as the loss function. A plot depicting the training and testing losses against the number of epochs is presented in **Figure 4.5(a)** to illustrate the model's convergence and generalization capabilities. The figure shows that both the training and testing losses decrease significantly over the epochs, reaching a very low MSE value of approximately 3.69×10^{-10} at epoch 1000. This very low MSE value indicates that the model has achieved a high level of accuracy. Additionally, it is apparent the model is not overfitting and has strong generalization ability because the training and testing loss curves closely aligned during the training period.

(a) A plot of training and testing loss curves

Training Progress			
Unit	Initial Value	Stopped Value	Target Value
Epoch	0	1000	1000
Elapsed Time	-	00:12:31	-
Performance	2.95	3.69e-10	0
Gradient	7.31	9.44e-07	1e-07
Mu	0.005	5e+04	1e+10
Effective # Param	356	355	0
Sum Squared P...	166	421	0

(b) Training window

Figure 4.5. Training window and loss curves

Additionally, it is visible from the training window in **Figure 4.5(b)** that the training process took 12 minutes, 31 seconds. These results indicate a significant improvement in accuracy and training time over existing models, as depicted in **Table 4.3**.

Table 4.3. Comparison Table for MSE and Training Time

SN	FNN model	Year	MSE (rad ²)	Training time
1	Shah [87]	2020	8.93×10^{-7}	NR
2	Lopez [88]	2021	2.00×10^{-4}	NR
3	Aggogeri [89]	2022	3.24×10^{-4}	NR
4	Kramar [90]	2022	2.36×10^{-3}	NR
5	Tagliani [63]	2022	1.74×10^{-6}	NR
6	Sharkawy [45]	2023	9.07×10^{-7}	44min, 16s
7	Proposed model	2024	3.69×10^{-10}	12min, 31s

Results for the joint space assessment are presented in **Table 4.4** and **Figure 4.6** reveal very low bias (ME) values all falling within a $\times 10^{-6}$ radians range for each joint, indicating high prediction accuracy. Additionally, the variance (STD) values are also very low, around $\times 10^{-4}$ radians for each joint, indicating highly precise and consistent predictions. Furthermore, the RMSE values are remarkably low, also in the order of $\times 10^{-4}$ for each joint. Interestingly, the RMSE values are very close to the STD values for each joint, further confirming that the model not only accurately predicts the actual joint configurations but does so repeatedly with high precision. Finally, **Figure 4.6** visually confirms these findings. The plot showcases a close alignment between the trajectory of the predicted joint angles and the trajectory of the actual joint angles, further solidifying the model's exceptional performance in joint space prediction. Results for the Cartesian space assessment are presented in Table 4.5 as well as **Figure 4.7** and **Figure 4.8**. **Table 4.5** indicates the model's effectiveness in forecasting the orientations of the robot for trajectory is similar to its performance in predicting the joint configurations for the trajectory. Again, the bias values fall within a range of $\times 10^{-6}$ radians, while both variance and RMSE are very close, falling within a range of $\times 10^{-4}$ radians. Thus, the orientations of the robot for the trajectory are predicted with high accuracy and precision by the model. This confirmed in **Figure 4.7** by illustrating the trajectory of the predicted roll, yaw, and pitch angles aligning closely with the trajectory of the actual orientations.

Table 4.4. Performance of Model in Joint Space

Metric	Theta 1 (rad)	Theta 2 (rad)	Theta 3 (rad)	Theta 4 (rad)	Theta 5 (rad)	Theta 6 (rad)
RMSE (e-04)	0.1698	0.1302	0.1640	0.2182	0.2272	0.2250
ME (e-06)	0.2461	-0.0726	-0.0770	0.0169	0.0380	-0.3243
STD (e-04)	0.1698	0.1302	0.1640	0.2182	0.2272	0.2250

Figure 4.6. Predicted vs. actual joint space trajectories

Table 4.5. Performance of Model in Cartesian Space

Metric	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Roll (rad)	Pitch (rad)	Yaw (rad)
RMSE	0.0401	0.0261	0.0458	0.3556e-04	0.2461e-04	0.3246e-04
ME	-0.3471e-03	0.5870e-03	-0.1781e-03	0.1365e-06	-0.1513e-06	0.0196e-06
STD	0.0401	0.0260	0.0458	0.3556e-04	0.2461e-04	0.3246e-04

Figure 4.7. Actual vs. predicted orientation trajectories

Figure 4.8. Actual vs. predicted Cartesian space trajectory

Table 4.5 shows that the model's performance in estimating the trajectory's Cartesian coordinates adheres to the previously identified pattern. The model demonstrates consistently low bias values, falling within a range of $\times 10^{-6}$ meters. Moreover, the STD

and RMSE values for Cartesian coordinates are also very close, both within a range of $\times 10^{-4}$ meters. The close alignment of the predicted and actual trajectory in Cartesian space, illustrated in **Figure 4.8** confirms the model is accurate and precise in forecasting the Cartesian coordinates of the trajectory.

Considering that the average of the STD values of the robot's positions throughout the trajectory is 0.0373 mm, which is significantly less than the 0.07 mm RT value, and the very low bias values, the model can potentially compensate for a larger portion of the robot's inconsistencies during execution. By providing a more accurate and consistent reference path, the model can help the robot's control system adjust for its limitations and achieve a path closer to the desired one.

It is also worth noting that for the same trajectory, the proposed ALM executed the IK in 1.2526 seconds, while the proposed FNN executed the IK in 0.3451 seconds. This means the FNN performed the task approximately 3.63 times faster than the ALM. This significant difference in execution time solidifies the suitability of FNNs for real-time control in task-specific IK problems of industrial robotics.

CHAPTER 5

5. CONCLUSION

The goal of this thesis is to optimize both task-free and task-specific inverse kinematics (IK) for precision control of industrial robotics. A novel Adaptive Levenberg-Marquardt (ALM) algorithm is presented for task-free IK, which provides solutions for all possible joint configurations for a target tool pose. Experimental evaluations conducted on the ABB IRB 6700 demonstrated that the proposed ALM algorithm shows significant improvements over existing iterative methods, specifically the standard, non-adaptive LM algorithm, and an existing ALM. It achieved superior accuracy, precision, and computational efficiency, even in near-singular configurations. The enhanced performance of the proposed ALM is attributed to its adaptive mechanism that dynamically adjusts the step size and damping factor. This makes the ALM a robust and efficient option for exploring all possible robot positions.

For task-specific IK, which focuses on finding the optimal joint configurations for a specific trajectory, a Feedforward Neural Network (FNN) model is presented. The FNN model achieved remarkably low bias, variance, and RMSE values, indicating high accuracy and precision in both joint and Cartesian space predictions. Notably, achieving this high level of accuracy was accomplished with a significantly reduced training time (12 minutes, 31 seconds) compared to existing models (44 minutes, 16 seconds). Furthermore, the comparison of the model's standard deviation with the ABB IRB 6700's path repeatability highlighted its potential to compensate for the robot's inherent limitations, thereby enhancing real-world trajectory execution and achieving paths closer to the desired ones. Additionally, the FNN performed the task-specific IK task approximately 3.63 times faster than the ALM, stressing its suitability for real-time control in task-specific IK problems.

The two proposed solutions, however, have limitations. Firstly, all experiments were conducted in a simulated environment, which may not fully capture real-world complexities. The performance of the algorithms in real-world applications must be validated, particularly in the presence of factors such as sensor noise, mechanical wear, and environmental variations. Additionally, the FNN model is only applicable to task-specific

IK, and not task-free IK problems, limiting its broader applicability. Finally, while the ALM algorithm is robust and converges quickly, it may encounter difficulties in highly dynamic contexts where real-time adjustments are required.

Future research could focus on implementing and validating the proposed algorithms on real-world robotic systems to assess their performance under operational conditions. This could involve extensive testing in varying industrial settings to ascertain their robustness and reliability. Furthermore, a larger range of IK problems can be solved by creating hybrid models that integrate the best features of both the ALM and FNN. For instance, leveraging the by combining the robustness and fast convergence of the ALM with the execution speed and prediction accuracy of the FNN, a more versatile and efficient IK solution could be developed. This solution could potentially outperform existing hybrid models in terms of speed, accuracy, and precision. The solution could also be applied to wider range of tasks beyond task-specific IK.

Exploring strategies for reinforcement learning to improve the performance and adaptability of IK algorithms could be another direction for future research. Through the use of reinforcement learning, the models could adapt to changes in its surroundings and enhance its performance over time, becoming more resilient to unforeseen challenges.

Thus, while the proposed ALM and FNN algorithms represent significant advancements in solving IK problems in industrial robotics, there is still room for improvement and further research. By addressing the limitations and exploring new methodologies, the field can move closer to achieving highly robust and reliable IK solutions for an extensive array of usage in industries.

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